

Downey and Tucker "Early life access to hay does not affect later life oral behavior in feed-restricted heifers"

Supplemental Table 1. Raw means, SE, and 95% CI for all oral behaviors scored, along with model outputs.

Raw behavior means (proportions), CI, and betaregression model results

Behavior	Treatment				DF	Betareg model results	
	Hay		Control			chisq	P-value
	Means (SE)	95% CI	Means (SE)	95% CI			
Tongue rolling	0.0023 (0.0006)	[0.0009,0.0036]	0.0012 (0.0004)	[0.0002,0.0021]	1, 21	1.4122	0.2347
NNOM: Bedding	0.0567 (0.0073)	[0.0410,0.0723]	0.0615 (0.0145)	[0.0271,0.0958]	1, 21	0.11	0.7401
NNOM: Other	0.0449 (0.0060)	[0.0321,0.0577]	0.0329 (0.0067)	[0.0171,0.0488]	1, 21	1.8136	0.1781
NNOM: Total	0.1290 (0.009)	[0.1092,0.1489]	0.1118 (0.0114)	[0.0847,0.1389]	1, 21	1.2614	0.2614
Tongue flicks	0.0110 (0.0016)	[0.0077,0.0144]	0.0115 (0.0017)	[0.0074,0.0156]	1, 21	0.2854	0.5932
Allogrooming	0.0342 (0.0033)	[0.0271,0.0412]	0.0319 (0.0061)	[0.0174,0.0464]	1, 21	0.4054	0.5243
Self grooming	0.0219 (0.0018)	[0.0180,0.0258]	0.0190 (0.0016)	[0.0153,0.0227]	1, 21	0.5475	0.4593
Drinking water	0.0174 (0.0021)	[0.0130,0.0218]	0.0145 (0.0021)	[0.0095,0.0194]	1, 21	0.6907	0.4059

Behavior	Treatment						Wilcoxon test results	
	Hay			Control			# doing behavior	P-value
	Means (SE)	95% CI	# doing behavior	Means (SE)	95% CI	# doing behavior		
Intersucking	0.0007 (0.0003)	[0.0002,0.0013]	12 (75%)	0.0006 (0.0003)	[0,0.0012]	4 (50%)	0.6851	
NNOM: Feed bin	0.0274 (0.0038)	[0.0194,0.0354]	16 (100%)	0.0174 (0.0016)	[0.0136,0.0212]	8 (100%)	0.2318	

Additional behaviors not modeled	Treatment			
	Hay		Control	
	Means (SE)	# doing behavior	Means (SE)	# doing behavior
Urine drinking	0.00002 (0.00002)	3 (19%)	0.00003 (0.00002)	2 (25%)

Correlations between calf and heifer behavior

Behavior	Age				Paired T-test or Wilcoxon test			Spearman rank correlation		
	Calf		Heifer		t or V	P-value	DF	r	P-value	DF
	Raw average (SE)	95% CI	Raw average (SE)	95% CI						
Drinking water	0.009 (0.0009)	[0.007,0.011]	0.016 (0.002)	[0.013,0.020]	5.68	<0.001	1,23	0.315	0.134	1,23
NNOM: Total	0.096 (0.007)	[0.080,0.111]	0.123 (0.007)	[0.108,0.138]	2.806	0.01	1,23	0.108	0.615	1,23
Groom: Self	0.040 (0.003)	[0.034,0.046]	0.021 (0.001)	[0.018,0.024]	-6.5211	<0.001	1,23	0.099	0.644	1,23
Tongue flicks	0.041 (0.002)	[0.037,0.046]	0.011 (0.006)	[0.009,0.014]	-13.702	<0.001	1,23	0.37	0.073	1,23
Tongue rolling	0.0004 (0.0002)	[0,0.0008]	0.002 (0.0004)	[0.001,0.003]	280	<0.001	---	0.17	0.428	---

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Supplemental Figure S1. Experimental pen setup. Diagram of pens. Each pen was visible via 3 camera angles covering the inside portion (e.g. Cam2; 2-2.3m above the ground), outside portion (e.g. Cam1; 2-2.3m above the ground), and full pen (e.g. Cam3; 3-4m above the ground). An example full pen camera angle (Cam3) is also shown.